

EARTH SCIENCES

PREDICTION OF DENSITY HETEROGENEOUSITY OF ROCKS ACCORDING TO GRAVITY PROSPECTING DATA

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the issue of predicting areas and boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks based on gravity survey data. This question belongs to the category of solving the inverse problem of gravity exploration, which, as is known, can be solved ambiguously. So, in this case everyone has to use a priori information in order to solve such a problem at the right level. To predict areas and boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks based on gravity survey data, two approaches are currently used. The first is the analytical continuation of the field into the lower half-space with the subsequent calculation of the full normalized gravity gradient, and the second is the use of a statistical connection between geological and geophysical data to predict the boundaries of the density heterogeneity of rocks.

Keywords: Gravity anomaly, analytical continuation, full normalized gradient, boundary prediction, density inhomogeneity.

Introduction

Analytical continuation of the potential field into the lower half-space followed by calculation of the full normalized gravity gradient along the profile is widely used in gravity exploration. Among these methods, the Berezkin method should be noted, according to which the observed gravity curve is subjected to a Fourier transform [2]. After this, the desired curve is represented as a sum of harmonic functions with various harmonics. This curve is then analytically continued into the lower half-space to various depths with a certain step. Next, at these depths, the full normalized gravity gradient is calculated, on the basis of which gradient maps along the section are constructed, which reflects the picture of the density heterogeneity of rocks. These maps highlight the maxima and minima of the total normalized gradient corresponding to areas of increasing or decreasing rock density. A sufficient number of publications are devoted to this problem [5,7,9-14].

Probability-statistical methods are used to predict interfaces with different densities. In this way, statistical relationships are determined between geological and geophysical data, such as, for example, between the gravity anomaly, or its transforms, and the depth of the interface between rocks with different densities according to seismic or drilling data. Such an analysis is first carried out on a reference territory with known values

of geological and geophysical parameters. Based on the principle of analogies, using correlations established on the standard, areas and boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks are predicted. In both cases, due to the complexity of the calculations, a computer is used. The use of gravimetric data to predict the boundaries of rock heterogeneity using mathematical methods is currently widely used [1,3,6,8,15-18].

Means, methods and results

To predict areas of density heterogeneity of rocks based on gravity survey data, the Department of Geophysics has developed the Force-Fortran PNG program, which allows, based on the observed curve along the profile, to calculate the values of the full normalized gravity gradient (FNG) in the lower half-space at various depths [7,10,12]. To test this program, a model of the gravity curve along the observation profile was first compiled using the EXCEL program (Fig. 1). As can be seen, the curve has the shape of maximum gravity. The length of the profile is 12 km, the intensity of the anomaly is 7 mGal. This curve possibly represents an oval body with positive excess density in the section being studied.

To work with the PNG program, the initial data was first prepared in accordance with the program input statements. These data and calculation results are shown below.

Fig.1. Profile gravity curve model

Initial data:

Number of point M= 11

Gravity values in integers

20000 30000 40000 50000 60000 70000 60000
50000 40000 30000
20000

Format factor FOR=10000.00 DX= 1.00

Starting, ending points and step along the profile in km

XH= 0.00 XZL= 9.00 DDX= 1.00

Start, end points and depth step of analytical continuation in km

ZH= 0.00 ZMAX= 7.00 HDZ 1.00

Initial, final number of harmonics and its step of change

NH= 10 NMAX= 30 ND= 10

Gravity values in mGals

2.0000 3.0000 4.0000 5.0000 6.0000 7.0000 6.0000
5.0000 4.0000 3.0000 2.0000

Gravity values without linear background

0.0000 1.0000 2.0000 3.0000 4.0000 5.0000 4.0000
3.0000 2.0000 1.0000 0.0000

Number of harmonics in Fourier expansion N=10

B_n - Fourier transform coefficients

4.0863 -0.0000 -0.4852 0.0000 0.2000 -0.0000 -0.1260
-0.0000 0.1025 0.0000

List= 1

Depth step of analytical continuation in km

0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 5.00 6.00 7.00

Values of the total normalized gravity gradient (in depth)

: 9.00: : 0.81 0.68 0.44 0.23 0.41 0.64 0.80 0.89
: 8.00: : 0.86 0.68 0.51 0.62 0.75 0.85 0.92 0.96
: 7.00: : 1.00 0.83 0.47 1.05 1.17 1.12 1.07 1.04
: 6.00: : 1.25 1.53 2.04 1.89 1.62 1.36 1.20 1.11
: 5.00: : 1.38 1.93 2.84 2.37 1.83 1.47 1.25 1.13
: 4.00: : 1.25 1.53 2.04 1.89 1.62 1.36 1.20 1.11
: 3.00: : 1.00 0.83 0.47 1.05 1.17 1.12 1.07 1.04
: 2.00: : 0.86 0.68 0.51 0.62 0.75 0.85 0.92 0.96
: 1.00: : 0.81 0.68 0.44 0.23 0.41 0.64 0.80 0.89
: 0.00: : 0.79 0.63 0.25 0.03 0.27 0.56 0.76 0.87

Number of harmonics in Fourier expansion N= 20

B_n - Fourier transform coefficients

4.0863-0.0000-0.4852 0.0000 0.2000-0.0000-0.1260
-0.0000 0.1025 0.0000-0.1025 0.0000 0.1260 0.0000
-0.2000 0.0000 0.4852-0.0000-4.0863 0.0000

List= 1

Depth step of analytical continuation in km

0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 5.00 6.00 7.00

Values of the total normalized gravity gradient (in depth)

: 9.00: : 0.76 0.56 0.77 0.87 0.93 0.96 0.98 0.99
: 8.00: : 0.80 0.66 0.85 0.93 0.97 0.98 0.99 1.00
: 7.00: : 0.91 0.88 1.02 1.03 1.02 1.01 1.01 1.00
: 6.00: : 1.12 1.43 1.27 1.14 1.08 1.04 1.02 1.01
: 5.00: : 2.08 2.41 1.43 1.20 1.10 1.05 1.03 1.01
: 4.00: : 1.12 1.43 1.27 1.14 1.08 1.04 1.02 1.01
: 3.00: : 0.91 0.88 1.02 1.03 1.02 1.01 1.01 1.00
: 2.00: : 0.80 0.66 0.85 0.93 0.97 0.98 0.99 1.00
: 1.00: : 0.76 0.56 0.77 0.87 0.93 0.96 0.98 0.99
: 0.00: : 0.74 0.53 0.74 0.85 0.92 0.95 0.97 0.99

Number of harmonics in Fourier expansion
N=30

B_n - Fourier transform coefficients

4.0863-0.0000-0.4852 0.0000 0.2000-0.0000-0.1260
-0.0000 0.1025 0.0000-0.1025 0.0000 0.1260 0.0000
-0.2000 0.0000 0.4852-0.0000-4.0863 0.0000 4.0863
-0.0000-0.4852-0.0000 0.2000 0.0000-0.1260-0.0000
0.1025 0.0000

List= 1

Depth step of analytical continuation in km

0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 5.00 6.00 7.00

Values of the total normalized gravity gradient (in depth)

: 9.00: : 0.38 0.43 0.55 0.37 0.32 0.62 0.79 0.89
: 8.00: : 0.77 0.80 0.80 0.90 0.77 0.84 0.91 0.95

: 7.00: : 1.17 1.17 0.92 0.35 1.07 1.11 1.07 1.04
: 6.00: : 1.59 1.59 1.51 1.71 1.64 1.39 1.21 1.12
: 5.00: : 2.16 1.86 2.03 2.92 2.09 1.53 1.27 1.14
: 4.00: : 1.59 1.59 1.51 1.71 1.64 1.39 1.21 1.12
: 3.00: : 1.17 1.17 0.92 0.35 1.07 1.11 1.07 1.04
: 2.00: : 0.77 0.80 0.80 0.90 0.77 0.84 0.91 0.95
: 1.00: : 0.38 0.43 0.55 0.37 0.32 0.62 0.79 0.89
: 0.00: : 0.03 0.18 0.43 0.41 0.33 0.55 0.75 0.86

As you can see, the initial number of harmonics is set to 10. The calculated values of the total normalized gravity gradient along the profile for this number of harmonics were entered into the SURFER graphic program and, based on the compiled “grid,” a map of the FNG field was constructed to a depth of 7 km with a step of 1 km (Fig. 2). As can be seen, at approximately a depth of 2 km, a large FNG maximum with an intensity of 2.8 dimensionless FNG units is clearly observed. This maximum on the left and right is outlined by two minima of the full normalized gradient with an intensity of approximately 0.4 FNG units, reflecting areas of decreased rock density.

Fig.2. Field of the full normalized gravity gradient from the model curve (number of harmonics 10)

The same picture is observed on the constructed map of vectors of the total normalized gravity gradient for the number of harmonics 10 (Fig. 3).

Fig.3.

Field of the full normalized gravity gradient from the model curve in vector form (number of harmonics 10)

Next, a similar FNG map was constructed for the number of harmonics equal to 20 (Fig. 4). As can be seen, the FNG maximum with an intensity of approximately 2.5 units has shifted upward to a depth of 1 km. As can be seen, the exact location of areas of density heterogeneity in rocks depends on the optimal selection

of the number of harmonics. Below is the constructed FNG section of the observed model curve for the number of harmonics $N=30$ (Fig. 5). As can be seen, the FNG

Fig.4. Field of the total normalized gravity gradient from the model curve (number of harmonics 20)

Fig.5. Field of the total normalized gravity gradient from the model curve (number of harmonics 30)

maximum shifted to a depth of 3 km and its intensity reached 3.0 FNG units. For the condition of the absence of a priori information, we have developed a technique for selecting the optimal number of harmonics according to the criterion of the maximum intensity of the APG values [10]. Therefore, in all likelihood, the depth of the heterogeneity zone is approximately 3 km.

To predict the boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks, as stated above, statistical methods are used to construct structural map on the base of gravity and seismic data or drilling data on the depth of the desired boundary of density heterogeneity. These methods are used in modifications of multidimensional regression analysis (MRA) and correlation methods of separation of anomalies (COMS) [1,16-18]. At the Geophysics department of the ASOIU, where such studies were constantly carried out because this technique makes it possible to predict the boundaries of heterogeneity in hard-to-reach areas (mountainous areas, cultivated areas, marshy areas, etc.), where there is a sufficient amount of gravity and magnetic survey data. To implement

these methods, appropriate software has been developed.

According to the MRA method, at the beginning, correlation connections are established between the depths of the boundaries of different sedimentary strata according to seismic exploration or drilling data also gravity anomalies and their results of processing, and in extrapolation of such connections to areas unstudied by seismic prospecting and drilling. Thereby the complex seismic geological conditions of individual areas of Azerbaijan, it is not possible to obtain unambiguous reference seismic data on the structure of the lower Mesozoic stage; the Department of Geophysics has developed a method of MRA with using only a representative part of conditional seismic horizons (CSH) with detailed and high-precision gravity reconnaissance. The representative part of density heterogeneity boundaries is understood as that part of the CSH which coincides in plan with the curve of the local gravity anomaly. The select of such a measure is based on the fact that in the case of one density contact boundary,

the local structure of the studied surface of density inhomogeneity in the gravitational field should be reflected in plan with much greater accuracy.

The correlation method of field separation (COMS) differs from methods of trend analysis in that it allows one to isolate from the observed field value a local anomaly that is best correlated with the depth of the inhomogeneity surface under study. According to the concept of correlation methods for converting anomalies, developed at the Moscow Institute of oil and gas named after Gubkina by I.I. Shraibman, M.S. Zhdanov, O.V. Vitvitsky, the initial gravitational field is represented as a sum [16]:

$$G_{\text{obs}} = G_{\text{res}} + G_{\text{back}}, \quad (1)$$

Here G_{obs} is the observed value of gravity parameter; G_{res} is a residual (local) component of gravity force; G_{back} is the regional component of gravity.

The background (regional) component of gravity is represented as a next polynomial:

$$G_{\text{back}} = \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(x, y) \quad (2)$$

Here: a_p are the coefficients of the transformation polynomial; $f_p(x, y)$ are a basis functions depending on x, y, x^2, xy, y^2 and et al; N is a length of the transformation polynomial; x, y are the coordinates of measuring points. This polynomial is called a transformation polynomial. The residual or local component of gravity may be presented below:

$$G_{\text{res}} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} b_i j_i + c, \quad (3)$$

Here b_i, c are the coefficients of the linear equation of regression; k is number of geological or geophysical parameters reflected the density heterogeneity; j_i is a corresponding geological or geophysical parameter.

The coefficients of the regression equations a_p, b_i, c are determined from the condition of the minimum standard deviation of functional F :

$$F = [G_{\text{obs}} - \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(x, y) - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} b_i j_i - c]^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (4)$$

To do this, the following condition must be met:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial c} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial a_p} = 0 \quad (p \in N), (i=1, 2, \dots, k-1) \\ \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial b_i} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

From this condition one can determine the coefficients a_p, b_i, c .

This way to finding regression coefficients is called COMR-A. Within the framework of correlation methods for dividing fields, another approach is possible (KOMR-B), when a geological parameter, for example H (the boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks) is considered as a function of its residual component G_{res} . For this case, the coefficients are determined from the condition:

$$\Phi = [H - b(G_{\text{obs}} - \sum_{p=1}^N a_p f_p(x, y) - c)]^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (6)$$

Nevertheless, in this approach the formulas for solving the system of equations became very complicated.

It should be noted that this approach is rational to use in the case when the boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks is well reflected in the gravity field.

When the studied complex of heterogeneities is faintly reflected in the gravity field, such as, for example, a highly dislocated Upper Mesozoic complex of sediments which lying below the eroded surface of Upper Cretaceous sediments ("P" horizon), the MRA method turned out to be more effective [1,16-18]. The desired burial depth of the boundary of heterogeneities H in this case is represented as a next polynomial:

$$H = a_0 + a_1 \cdot \Delta g_{\text{Boug}} + a_2 \cdot \Delta g_5 + a_3 \cdot \Delta g_{\text{Boug}}^2 + a_4 \Delta g_{\text{Boug}} \cdot \Delta g_5 + a_5 \cdot \Delta g_5^2 \dots \quad (7)$$

Where a_0, a_i are the regression equation coefficients; $\Delta g_{\text{Boug}}, \Delta g_5$ are Bouguer anomaly, local anomaly and other gravity transformers.

The essence of correlation methods for predicting the boundaries of density inhomogeneities of rocks can be illustrated by the example of a model of a separate seismic-gravimetric profile profile (Fig. 6). The quantized values of the initial data are shown below (Table 1). This figure shows a gravity curve along a 10 km profile, and at the bottom of the section the interface between two media with different densities is shown. As can be seen, there is a correlation between gravity survey data and the depth of the interface according to seismic survey or drilling data. Moreover, from a mathematical point of view, this relationship will be inverse, so we will predict this boundary using the formula:

$$H_{\text{pi}} = \frac{a}{\Delta g_i} \quad (8)$$

Here H_{pi} are the predicted depth values; Δg_i - gravity values; a is the coefficient of the regression equation.

Fig.6. Model of a separate seismic -gravimetric profile

Table 1

Values of gravity and depth of the density boundary on the reference profile

№	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Δg_i	1.9	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.6	1.9	2.3	2.4	2.2	1.8
H_i	-2.0	-3.0	-3.5	-3.5	-3.2	-2.5	-2.0	-1.7	-2.0	-2.5

The coefficient of the regression equation is found using the least squares method using the formula:

$$a = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{H_i}{\Delta g_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\Delta g_i^2}}, \quad (8)$$

where $H_i, \Delta g_i$ are the current values of depth and gravity on the model reference profile.

Using this formula on the computer, the calculated value is $a = 4.67$. The results of calculating the predicted values of the interface depth and the initial data are shown below (Table 2). Based on the calculation results using the EXCEL program, a graph of the predicted seismogravimetric profile was constructed (Fig. 7). As can be seen, the predicted interface between the two media (shown in black on the graph) coincides well with the actual boundary and the standard deviation does not exceed approximately 200 m.

Table 2

Results of calculation of predicted values of interface depth

№	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Δg_i	1.9	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.6	1.9	2.3	2.4	2.2	1.8
H_i	-2.0	-3.0	-3.5	-3.5	-3.2	-2.5	-2.0	-1.7	-2.0	-2.5
$H_{i\text{progn}}$	-2.4	-2.9	-3.3	-3.3	-2.9	-2.5	-2.0	-1.9	-2.1	-2.6

Fig.7. Predictive seismic-gravimetric profile model

Conclusions:

1. Methods for predicting areas and boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks based on gravity survey data are analyzed. It is shown that these methods belong to the class of problems for solving inverse problems of gravity exploration.

2. The model curve along the gravity profile with a length of 8 km was compiled to predict areas of density heterogeneity of rocks using the GNORM Force-Fortran program, which developed at the Department of Geophysics.

3. Based on the compiled model of the gravity curve, the initial data were prepared for work using the GNORM program in accordance with the input operators and calculations of the full normalized gravity gradient along the profile were performed for the number of harmonics 10, 20 and 30 in the Fourier expansion.

4. Based on the results of calculating the values of the full normalized gravity gradient using a graphical program, sections of the full normalized gravity gradient along the profile were constructed for depths up to 7 km with a step of 1 km. Analysis of these sections showed, firstly, the effectiveness of the GNORM program for predicting areas of density heterogeneity of rocks, and secondly, the possibility of selecting the optimal number of harmonics in the absence or insufficiency of a priori information.

5. The mathematical foundations of methods for interpreting gravimetric data in combination with seismic geological data are considered by establishing correlations between them to predict the geological boundaries of density heterogeneity of rocks on the bases of results of statistical analysis.

6. Correlation methods of interpreting gravitational data, correlation methods of field separation and multidimensional regression analysis are analyzed, as well as algorithmic support for these method was developed at the Department of Geophysics.

7. A correlation connection has been established between gravity and seismic model data on the reference profile of the study. A feedback relationship has been established between geophysical data on this profile. Based on the established feedback, the values of the depths of the interface of the density heterogeneity of rocks were predicted using modern graphical software.

8. The research results obtained can be used to guide further gravimetric survey and to identify oil and gas promising areas of density heterogeneity of rocks.

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